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EASITRAIN

European Advanced Superconductor Innovation & Training

FORM

INTERMEDIARY TRAINING EVALUATION

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Abstract:

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The training feedback form has been developed by the project coordinator based on best practices of LERU universities such as the University of Geneva (Switzerland) and the formal quality process for future e-LERU virtual campus (GA 2004-3086 / 001-002 ELE-ELEB 12), D4.3 of the FOSTER EU project (GA 612425), the Central European University (Hungary) and the University of Genoa (Italy, document A.A. 2018-2019). General training evaluation feedback has been based on the EC H2020 MSCA ITN Self-evaluation form, Version 1.0 (12 October 2017).

With respect to the evaluation, the project considers the training as a fine blend of four integral parts:

1. Training through active participation in a research project at the employer site,
2. Training through participation in an academic doctorate programme,
3. Training through network-wide organised events, courses and collaborative interaction,
4. Specialised trainings at the local employer site.

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1. PART 1: EVALUATION OF THE MSCA ITN ACTION

Following the general H2020 MSCA project evaluation criteria, the following questions serve capturing the value of the project at high level.

1.1. EXCELLENCE

Q1.1 From your personal perspective, does your research project in this ITN adequately address quality, innovative aspects and a credible research programme including inter- and multidisciplinary, intersectoral, where appropriate, gender aspects?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Choose an item.

Q1.2 From your personal perspective, does the doctoral study programme in this ITN Training Network (ITN) adequately address quality, innovative aspects and a credible research programme including inter- and multidisciplinary, intersectoral, where appropriate, gender aspects?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Choose an item.

Q1.3 From your personal perspective, do the local trainings at your employer site in this ITN adequately address quality, innovative aspects and a credible research programme including inter- and multidisciplinary, intersectoral, where appropriate, gender aspects?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Choose an item.

Q1.4 From your personal perspective, do the project-wide organised trainings in this ITN adequately address quality, innovative aspects and a credible research programme including inter- and multidisciplinary, intersectoral, where appropriate, gender aspects?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Choose an item.

Q1.5 From your personal perspective, do the secondment periods in this ITN adequately expose you to other environments, in particular to other sectors than your working domain (if no secondment performed so far, provide your forward-looking estimation with respect to the planned secondment periods)?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Choose an item.

Q1.6 From your personal perspective, are the secondment periods in this ITN relevant for your personal career development (if no secondment performed so far, provide your forward-looking estimation with respect to the planned secondment periods)?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Choose an item.

Q1.7 From your personal perspective, are the secondment periods in this ITN feasible for you in terms of time and budget (if no secondment performed so far, provide your forward-looking estimation with respect to the planned secondment periods)?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Choose an item.

Q1.8 From your personal perspective, are the secondment periods in this ITN in line with your research project objectives (if no secondment performed so far, provide your forward-looking estimation with respect to the planned secondment periods)?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Choose an item.

Q1.9 Do you perceive the secondment periods in this ITN as an added value (if no secondment performed so far, provide your forward-looking estimation with respect to the planned secondment periods)?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Choose an item.

Q1.10 Please rate the quality of the research project supervision at your employer site.

Rating scale: 0 = Not adequate, 1 = Rather not adequate, 2 = Rather adequate, 3 = Adequate

Choose an item.

Q1.11 Please rate the quality of the doctoral programme supervision at the university (if the supervision is carried out by the same person who is supervising the research project, please indicate the same score as in Q1.10).

Rating scale: 0 = Not adequate, 1 = Rather not adequate, 2 = Rather adequate, 3 = Adequate

Choose an item.

Q1.12 From your personal perspective, please rate the level of interaction between the participation organisations in this ITN.

Rating scale: 0 = Not adequate or not visible, 1 = Rather not adequate or only little visible, 2 = Rather adequate, 3 = Adequate

Choose an item.

1.2. IMPACT

Q2.1 From your perspective, does this ITN project enhance your career perspectives and employability?

Rating scale: 0 = Unlikely, 1 = Rather not likely, 2 = Rather likely, 3 = Likely

Choose an item.

Q2.2 From your perspective, does this ITN project contribute to the development of skills that are likely to enhance your career perspectives and employability?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Choose an item.

Q2.3 According to your impression, does this ITN contribute to structuring doctoral and early-stage research training at European level?

Rating scale: 0 = Unlikely, 1 = Rather not likely, 2 = Rather likely, 3 = Likely

Choose an item.

Q2.4 According to your impression, does this ITN make a meaningful contribution of the non-academic sector for doctoral and research training?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Choose an item.

Q2.5 According to your impression, does this ITN contribute to the development of a sustainable doctoral degree structure in Europe?

Rating scale: 0 = Unlikely, 1 = Rather not likely, 2 = Rather likely, 3 = Likely

Choose an item.

Q2.6 According to your impression, does this ITN disseminate adequately (dissemination = sharing of research work and results during the project duration with peers in research, industry or other commercial fields)?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Choose an item.

Q2.7 According to your impression, does this ITN foresee appropriate measures to exploit the research results (exploitation = the use of any work and findings for commercial purposes or in public policymaking including the use for other research activities)?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Please rate with a number (0 to 3): Choose an item.

Q2.8 According to your impression, does this ITN implement appropriate measures to communicate the project activities to different target audiences?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Please rate with a number (0 to 3): Choose an item.

1.3. QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY

Q3.1 According to your experience in this project, is the work plan of this ITN coherent with respect to a research goal or interlinked research goals?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Please rate with a number (0 to 3) : Choose an item.

Q3.2 According to your experience in this project, is the work plan of this ITN appropriately defined for the allocation of tasks and human resources to pursue the set research goals?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Please rate with a number (0 to 3) : Choose an item.

Q3.3 According to your experience in this project, are the infrastructures at the site at which you carry out the research appropriate for the defined work?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Please rate with a number (0 to 3) : Choose an item.

Q3.4 According to your experience in this project, is the organisation at which you perform your research sufficiently competent and experienced for the defined research?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Please rate with a number (0 to 3) : Choose an item.

Q3.5 According to your experience in the collaborative research in this project, is the organisation at which you perform your research complementary with respect to the other organisations that participate in the defined research in this project?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Please rate with a number (0 to 3) : Choose an item.

Q3.6 According to your experience in the collaborative research in this project, are the other organisations that participate in this ITN and with which you interact sufficiently competent and experienced for the defined research?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Please rate with a number (0 to 3) : Choose an item.

Q3.7 According to your experience in the collaborative research in this project, do the other organisations that participate in this ITN and with which you interact complement the activities at your organisation with respect to the defined research in this project?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Please rate with a number (0 to 3) : Choose an item.

Q3.8 According to your impression, is the organisation at which you are employed in this project committed to the research programme in this project?

Rating scale: 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Please rate with a number (0 to 3) : Choose an item.

Q3.9 According to your experience in the collaborative research in this project, are the other organisations in this project with which you interact for your research committed to the research programme in this project?

Rating scale : 0 = No, 1 = Rather no, 2 = Rather yes, 3 = Yes

Please rate with a number (0 to 3) : Choose an item.

1.4. STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES OF THIS ITN

Please indicate as brief bullet points up to five strengths in this Innovative Training Network project (less than 5 bullet points are possible):

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5.

Please indicate as brief bullet points up to five weaknesses in this Innovative Training Network project (less than 5 bullet points are possible):

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5.

2. PART B – THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC VALUE OF COLLABORATIVE, INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH

This part aims at gathering information about the socio-economic value of training in MSCA ITN actions in general and in this project in particular.

2.1. YOUR SKILLS

Please use the following scale to answer the questions in 5.1:

0 = not important,

1 = fairly important,

2 = rather important,

3 = important,

4 = very important

Q5.1 How do you rate the importance to engage in an MSCA ITN that is characterised by practical research projects in an international research consortium, combined with a doctoral study programme, local and network trainings?

Q5.1.1 Working in an international environment

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.1.2 Possibility to work with world class scientists and engineers

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.1.3 Value of CERN as host of an internationally coordinated research programme, carried out by an international consortium of complementary organisations

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.1.4 Development of new professional skills beyond the core scientific research domain

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.1.5 Deepening the knowledge and competences in the core domain of your interest

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.2 Compared to doctoral students who carry out their studies only at the university, NOT spending a research period at a research organisation or company, in your opinion, to what extent do you believe does the experience in this project improve your following skills?

Please use the following scale to answer the questions in 5.2:

0 = not at all,

1 = to a small extent,

2 = to a moderate extent,

3 = to a high extent,

4 = fully

Q5.2.1 Scientific research skills

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.2.2 Technical and engineering skills

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.2.3 Communication skills

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.2.4 Problem-solving capacity

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.2.5 Conflict-solving capacity

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.2.6 Team or project leadership skills

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.2.7 Developing, maintaining and using networks of collaborations

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.2.8 Independent thinking and critical analysis

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.2.9 Effectiveness and persistency in professional activities

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.2.10 Adapting to constraints

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.2.11 Creativity

Rating (0 to 4): Choose an item.

Q5.3 Which specific skills have you or are you acquiring in this MSCA ITN project (multiple selection is possible)

- Theoretical physics
- Experimental physics
- Foreign languages
- Political and social affairs
- Accounting and finance
- Informatics (including any software engineering related skills such as programming, program architecture and design, software organisation, use of software packages, data analytics, data acquisition, control systems, supervisory controls etc.)
- Information and communications technologies (IT technologies other than software-oriented ones)
- Semiconductor technologies
- Law (including contract management)
- Intellectual properties management
- Human resources
- Marketing and communication (including at scientific level)
- Healthcare
- Environmental engineering
- Architecture
- Design
- Mechanical engineering
- Cryogenics
- Vacuum technologies
- Optics
- Nuclear engineering (excluding radiation protection)
- Electrical and/or electronic engineering
- Chemistry
- Material technologies
- Manufacturing or production technologies
- Arts and humanities
- Business administration (including procurement)
- General management (including project management, team leading)
- Quality management with formal methods

- Risk management with formal methods
 - Occupational health and safety (excluding radiation protection)
 - Radiation protection
 - Economics
- Others (please list): _____

Q5.4 In recent socio-economic impact analysis studies that CERN carried out with the help of organisations who are specialised in quantitative economics, the effect of training in collaborative international research projects was analysed. The effect can be captured in the form of a « lifetime salary premium », i.e. in the sum of the salary that a person earns during her/his active working period until retirement that is higher than the one of a person with the same academic education level, but without involvement in a collaborative international research activity during the early research stage.

If you had to estimate the impact of your experience in this specific MSCA ITN project on your « lifetime salary », how many percent more do you believe you will probably earn over your future career compared to doctoral students who do not participate in an ITN project of this kind ? Please indicate your personal estimate based on the following options:

0 = 0%, no effect on my lifetime salary with respect to not having participated in this ITN or I am not able to provide an estimate

1 = 5%

2 = 10%

3 = 15%

4 = 20%

5 = more than 20 %

Choose an item.

3. PART C - GENERAL REMARKS

Please provide any remarks, clarifications and suggestions below. Please limit the text to **1500 characters** including spaces. Your factual text will be included unmodified in the deliverable report to the European Commission.